

CARBON NANOTUBE/POLYAMIDE 6 NANOCOMPOSITES VIA IN-SITU ANIONIC POLYMERISATION

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ABSTRACT

A key challenge in the development of nano-material reinforced composites is achieving adequate dispersion of the reinforcing component. This is particularly problematic for thermoplastic composites where the high melt viscosities of polymer matrices lead to a large energy requirement for the dispersion of the nanoparticles. The reactive processing of thermoplastics, where the final polymer is synthesised *in situ* by means of a by-product free reaction scheme is a new avenue currently in development as a low viscosity method for manufacturing continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites, and may also be advantageous for the manufacture of nanocomposites.

The application of the anionic polymerisation of ϵ -caprolactam has been explored for use in the manufacture of multi-walled carbon nanotube-reinforced (MWCNT) polyamide-6. An improvement in ultimate tensile strength of +23% and energy absorbed at break (a toughness indicator) of +86% was observed for the composites compounded by ball-milling prior to the polymerisation reaction. Some evidence of incomplete reaction was observed with a reduction (-10%) in tensile modulus from the ball-milled composite when compared to the neat polymer highlighting ongoing processing challenges. These process challenges are apparent in the sonicated sample, showcasing a sharp decrease in stiffness and strength, with a modest gain in toughness and elongation at break.

Whilst good macro-dispersion was achieved in the ball-mill compounded composites, definite improvement is possible with agglomerates 1-5 micron diameter observed by optical microscopy. Sonication alone was shown to be insufficient for obtaining adequate macro dispersion in this system.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polyamide-6 (PA6) is a versatile engineering polymer excelling in measures of toughness, abrasion resistance, and strength. These and others of its properties may be further improved by the addition of modifiers. Unfortunately, the incorporation of such modifiers to form thermoplastic composites is limited by the high viscosities of the melt-mixing processes, which in turn lead to poor dispersion and distribution of the modifiers within the matrix [1].

Recently, reactive processing of PA6 has been explored for the manufacturing of fibre reinforced plastics [2], rotomolded parts [3], and nanocomposites [4-6], amongst other applications. This reactive processing technique centres on the anionic polymerisation of ϵ -caprolactam monomer *in situ* (in mould or 'in compounding operation') to directly form the PA6 and its composites.

Carbon nanotubes (CNT)-reinforced PA6 composites represent a versatile new sub-class of polymeric materials with further enhanced mechanical and transport properties. Thus, *in situ* anionic polymerisation of ϵ -caprolactam is potentially a powerful technique for manufacturing well-dispersed nano-reinforced APA6 composites. Therefore, in this study, we present the effect of two different dispersion techniques (ball-milling vs. sonication) of CNTs in the monomer prior to reaction on the microstructure and mechanical properties of their reactively formed composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

The handling of all materials was conducted in an MBraun Dry Argon Glovebox to ensure moisture and oxygen did not interfere with the reaction. The Brugollen C™ reactive system was used with ϵ -caprolactam (CL), sodium caprolactamate (CLNa) in ‘C10’, and a caprolactam-blocked diisocyanate in ‘C20P’, all as supplied by Brüggemann Chemicals (C10 and C20P contains 1.3 and 2.0 mol active ingredient/kg ϵ -caprolactam, respectively). The reactant ratio used is presented in Table 1. The carbon nanotubes were TNM5 (multi-walled, OD: 20-30 nm) supplied by TimesNano (China). A loading of 1 wt% CNTs was used for the composite specimens.

	Mass Added
CL	29.7 g
C10	0.68 g
C20P	0.45 g
CNT* (TNM5)	0.3 g

*Neat ratio the same without added nanotubes

Table 1: Mixture Preparation

2.2 Dispersion of Nanomaterial

Prior to reaction, the nanotubes were pre-dispersed within the monomer. Two techniques were explored:

- A) The dry CNT/monomer mixture was added into a sealed vessel suitable for ball-milling (Fritsch Pulverisette 5/2). The ball mill was run for 8 hours at 150 rpm using six 10-mm diameter stainless steel balls. The ball-milled vessel was then returned to the glovebox and transferred for reaction.
- B) The CNT/monomer mixture was added to a beaker with a silicone gasket designed to fit the sonication horn (20 kHz, Vibracell VC750) and sealed inside the glovebox. The vessel was removed from the glovebox and transferred to a hot plate set at 130 C with an Argon purge line and allowed to melt. The gasket was pierced with the sonication horn and submerged into the molten mixture. The sonication was run for 9 minutes. The vessel was quickly resealed, returned to the glovebox and transferred for reaction.

2.3 Polymerisation Reaction

To conduct the polymerisation, the reactive mixtures (with C10 and C20P added) were pre-melted at 80 °C in an electric oven. The mixtures were stirred using a magnetic stirrer. The vessels were then transferred to a hot plate at 190 °C in order to complete the reaction. The vessel was promptly insulated with an aluminium foil jacket to control thermal loss. The sample was kept at heat for at least 25 minutes to allow for the reaction (5 minutes) and any subsequent primary and secondary crystallisation processes. The hot plate was turned off and the mixture was allowed to return to ambient temperature.

2.4 Microscopy

Small pellets were cut from the reacted composites and subsequently hot-pressed at 235 °C and 8 tons to create ~ 50 μ m thick films. The composite films were analysed by optical microscopy on an Olympus BX61 microscope in transmission mode.

2.4 Tensile Testing

The same pellets were injection moulded (280 °C) into tensile dogbones (ISO 527-2, Type 1BA). A minimum of 5 specimens per composite type were tested. The testing was conducted on an Instron

5584 at a crosshead speed of 10 mm/min and 1 kN load cell. The tensile specimens were tested “dry as moulded, DAM”.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Optical Micrographs

Representative optical micrographs of the composite films are presented in Fig. 1. The quality of the macro-dispersion is obvious in the ball-milled composites. The micrographs display a very consistent morphological texture, and good distribution of the CNTs agglomerates, of less than 20 μm in size. Excellent transparency of the films was a very interesting finding. Ball-milling provides a non-localised combination of impact and shear on the mixture, which may be the reason for the uniformity and dispersion levels attained. In contrast, in the sonicated composites, a sheared and flow-like patterned is observed. The initial agglomerates appear exfoliated and ruptured, but in this case the CNT distribution does not seem adequate enough, and the size distribution of the final agglomerates is much broader. This had a significant impact on the transparency of the films, as it was notably less than that of the ball-milled grade. This is a direct result of the highly localised shearing stresses applied by the sonicating horn on the mixture.

3.2 Tensile Testing

The tensile results are presented in Figure 2 with the mechanical properties summarised in Table 2. It is clear that the sonicated composites are significantly softer than the ball-milled composites and the APA6, with a significantly lower modulus and yield stress. This may almost certainly be attributed to reduced monomer conversion, with excess monomer acting as a plasticiser, and the polymer ultimately having a reduced molecular weight. It is postulated that some oxygen and moisture exposure occurred during the sonication procedure – further refinement of the experimental procedure would be required to infer that the sonication of the mixture itself lead to the reduced conversion. Conversely, the ball-milled CNT composite out-performed the neat specimen on strain at break (by +66%), energy absorbed (+86%), and ultimate tensile strength (+23%). The lower modulus (-10%) however is atypical for these nanocomposites, perhaps evidence of reduced conversion in the ball-milled composites as well or as a result of the formation of a different crystalline phase.

	Apparent Modulus		Yield Stress		Ultimate Tensile Strength		Strain at Break		Toughness (Energy)	
	(MPa)		(MPa)		(MPa)		(%)		(J.m ⁻³)	
	E	SE	σ_y	SE	σ_{UTS}	SE	ϵ_B	SE	τ	SE
Neat APA6										
<i>Unprocessed</i>	2100	(30)	60	(1.2)	61	(0.6)	94	(19)	50	(10.1)
CNT-APA6										
<i>Sonicated</i>	1300	(70)	34	(0.7)	58	(2.1)	124	(17)	61	(9.1)
<i>Ball-Milled</i>	1900	(90)	60	(0.3)	75	(2.2)	156	(15)	93	(6.9)

Table 2: Quantitative Summary of Tensile Results including Standard Error (SE)

Figure 1: Optical micrographs of the reacted composites at 1 wt% CNT by a) ball milling, and b) sonication.

Figure 2: Tensile Curves of the Neat APA6 Specimen (a) and APA6 Nanocomposites (sonicated (b), ball-milled (c)). Strain here is calculated by cross-head displacement over gauge length, and stress by force over initial average cross-sectional area. The sharp drops observed in (b) are attributed to the specimen slipping the specimen grips.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results here showcased the application of in situ polymerisation to achieve excellent macro-dispersion of CNT in polyamide 6 composites. The preliminary testing showed promise, with the reacted ball-milled CNT-APA6 composites displaying excellent macro-dispersion levels and outperforming the APA6 control in terms of tensile strength and toughness by 23% and 86%, respectively, at only 1 wt% CNTs. This is likely due to the quality of dispersion achieved. However, significant softening of the matrix was observed in the reacted sonicated CNT-APA6 composites. Further experimentation is required to rule out the effects of the additional melting stage of the monomer in the sonication process, and the effect of the dispersed CNTs themselves on both the propagation of the reaction and crystallisation of the matrix.

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